

Journalism Science Alliance

**PROGRAMME
WEBSITE**

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project name	Journalism and Science Alliance
Project acronym	JSA
Grant number	101180216
Project coordinator	António Granado, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa
Project duration	01/04/2025 - 31/03/2027

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable name and number	D5.1. Website		
Due date	31/05/2025		
Actual submission date	06/06/2025		
Contributing partners	UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA, EUROPEAN JOURNALISM CENTRE		
Deliverable type	R	Document, report	
	DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
	DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos etc.	X
	OTHER		
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

DELIVERABLE D5.1.: WEBSITE

The JSA website was developed by UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA and is available at the following link:

<https://journalismsciencealliance.eu/>

DISCLAIMER

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA). Neither the European Union nor EACEA can be held responsible for them.